

Development of Buck Boost Circuit with AVR Microcontroller

(Pembangunan Litar Buck Boost menggunakan mikropengawal AVR)

Muhammad Anas Sahabuden, Yushaizad Yusof
Faculty of Engineering & Built Environment, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia

ABSTRACT

The need of variable of DC(Direct Current) voltage is keep increasing with technology advancement of devices and equipment. The DC-DC Buck-Boost Converter is the solution to gain a suitable voltage on each application. Due to unstable control of a Buck Boost Converter a very complex digital signal processing had to be used to encounter this problem thus make a simple Buck boost Converter cost more than its worth. In this project a full concept of understanding and parameter decision is the first important thing been carried out to ease the process of mathematical modelling of the whole converter circuit. MATLAB Simulink is the primary software used to simulate the converter circuit and get the proper condition and specification of devices such as resistor, capacitor, inductor, Schottky Diode and Power MOSFET. The use of AVR Microcontroller is the best way to achieve a low cost stable control. AVR Microcontroller is easily programmed using Arduino as ISP (In-System-Programmer) and cost a lot more less compared to other type of microcontroller. The developed prototype for the designed Buck Boost Converter is tested with various load and multiple switching duty ratio. The findings is according to simulated design considering non-ideal condition.

Keywords: Buck Boost; Converter; Microcontroller; Direct Current Converter; MATLAB Simulink

ABSTRAK

Keperluan voltan AT(Arus Terus) semakin meningkat dengan kemajuan teknologi pelbagai peranti dan peralatan. Penukar Kuasa AT-AT adalah penyelesaian bagi mendapatkan voltan bersesuaian untuk setiap jenis aplikasi. Ketidakstabilan sistem kawalan bagi penukar kuasa Buck Boost memerlukan pemprosesan isyarat digital yang kompleks bagi menyelesaikan masalah tersebut dan menyebabkan kos penukar kuasa Buck Boost menjadi tinggi. Dalam kajian ini pemahaman konsep penuh dan penentuan parameter adalah perkara penting yang dijalankan bagi memudahkan proses pemodelan matematik litar penukar kuasa secara keseluruhan. MATLAB Simulink adalah perisian utama digunakan bagi mensimulasi litar penukar kuasa dan mendapatkan keadaan dan spesifikasi peranti seperti perintang, kapasitor, induktor, Schottky Diod dan MOSFET kuasa. Penggunaan mikropengawal adalah satu cara terbaik bagi mendapatkan sistem kawalan stabil berkos rendah. Mikropengawal AVR dapat diprogramkan dengan mudah menggunakan Arduino sebagai pengaturcara dalam sistem dan menjadikan kos pengawal ini adalah jauh lebih rendah dari mikropengawal yang lain. Prototaip penukar kuasa Buck Boost telah dibangunkan mengikut reka bentuk yang disimulasi dan diuji dengan beban dan kitar tugas yang pelbagai. Perkakasan yang dibangunkan dipastikan mengikut ciri simulasi selepas mengambil kira faktor keadaan sebenar.

Kata kunci: Buck Boost; Penukar Kuasa; Mikropengawal; Penukar Kuasa Arus Terus; MATLAB Simulink

INTRODUCTION

Power Electronic System having the ability to change, process and control the flow of electric power by giving voltage and current supply in optimum rate accordingly to the load. DC-DC converter is one type of electronic circuit that use to convert input voltage to a higher or lower output voltage. A DC-DC converter is the most commonly used in the application for latest technology due to its ability to convert the voltage in higher or lower rate. Before the development of DC-DC converter the use of vibrator, step up transformer and rectifier

is being used to convert DC to DC. This method need to convert the DC to AC before convert it back to DC.

DC-DC converter is divided into several type including Buck Converter, Boost Converter and Buck-Boost Converter. In general most of converters is used in portable devices such as mobile phone and personal computer where the main power comes from battery. Decision in type of power converter to be used is important to have the ultimate efficiency for the specific application needed for. This study is focusing on Buck-Boost Converter to

be used for multiple application with minimum cost. Many Buck Boost converter design have an issue where the cost of a converter is high due to complex digital signal processing applied. The ability to use an AVR microcontroller to overcome this problem is a good solution. (Karim et al,2014)

In this study, the AVR microcontroller is used in the design of the Buck Boost Converter. This eliminates unnecessary extra hardware that can increase the cost of a converter. The Buck Boost converter need to operate with a pulse that can be generated from a microcontroller and the same microcontroller can have the control of the switching in a closed loop. The AVR microcontroller can be easily programmed with the help of Arduino as an In-System Program. The circuit design is simulated before the prototype being developed to get the true concept and ease the process of parameter decision.

FIGURE 1 : Basic Buck Boost Circuit

CONCEPT UNDERSTANDING

Buck Boost Converter has the ability to give an output voltage that are higher or lower compare to input voltage. Buck Boost converter will give out an negative output. The circuit operate in two mods. Mod 1 is switch ON and Mod 2 switch OFF. FIGURE 1 show the Schematic of basic Buck Boost and the flow of current according to state.

On - State:

The input voltage source is directly connected to the inductor (L). This results in accumulating energy in L. In this stage, the capacitor supplies energy to the output load.(Sharif, 2013)

Off – State:

the inductor is connected to the output load and capacitor, so energy is transferred from L to C and R.

MATHEMATICAL MODELLING

When the switch is closed, the voltage across the inductor is

$$v_L = V_s = L \frac{di_L}{dt} \tag{1}$$

The rate of change of inductor current is a constant, indicating a linearly increasing inductor current. The preceding equation can be expressed as

METHODOLOGY

All the process in developing a buck boost Converter using an AVR microcontroller is done by using a systematic method to ensure all the findings is applied proportionally to the needs.(Eng Sheh et al,2015)

The process is started by concept understanding for a Buck Boost Converter by using multiple sources such as previous findings and power electronic books. After that a mathematical modelling for the concept is necessary in order to understand the system control and the system order.

MATLAB Simulink is used for the purpose of verification before developing the prototype. The developed prototype then tested and been analysed.

Power flow during On-State and Off-State

$$\frac{\Delta i_L}{\Delta t} = \frac{\Delta i_L}{DT} = \frac{V_s}{L} \tag{2}$$

Solving for Δi_L when the switch is closed gives

$$(\Delta i_L)_{closed} = \frac{V_s DT}{L} \tag{3}$$

When the switch is open, the current in the inductor cannot change instantaneously, resulting in a forward-biased diode and current into the resistor and capacitor. In this condition, the voltage across the inductor is

$$v_L = V_o = L \frac{di_L}{dt} \tag{4}$$

the rate of change of inductor current is constant, and the change in current is

$$\frac{\Delta i_L}{\Delta t} = \frac{\Delta i_L}{(1-D)T} = \frac{V_o}{L} \tag{5}$$

Solving for Δi_L ,

$$(\Delta i_L)_{open} = \frac{V_o(1-D)T}{L} \tag{6}$$

For steady-state operation, the net change in inductor current must be zero over one period.

$$(\Delta i_L)_{closed} + (\Delta i_L)_{open} = 0 \tag{7}$$

$$\frac{V_s DT}{L} + \frac{V_o(1-D)T}{L} = 0$$

Solving for V_o ,

$$V_o = -V_s \left(\frac{D}{1-D} \right) \quad (8)$$

Applying Laplace Transform

$$V_s = V_L + V_o \quad (9)$$

$$V_o = \frac{i_c}{sC} = i_o R \quad (10)$$

$$i_s = i_c + i_o \quad (11)$$

$$i_s = sCV_o + \frac{V_o}{R} \quad (12)$$

$$V_s = sLi_s + V_o \quad (13)$$

$$= sL(sCV_o + \frac{V_o}{R}) + V_o \quad (14)$$

$$= S^2LCV_o + \frac{SLV_o}{R} + V_o \quad (15)$$

$$= V_o (S^2LC + \frac{SL}{R} + 1) \quad (16)$$

Transfer function for Buck Boost

$$\frac{V_o}{V_s} = \frac{1}{S^2LC + \frac{SL}{R} + 1} \quad (17)$$

SIMULATION

MATLAB Simulink used for the simulation to get the working principle of the Buck Boost Converter. For the simulation the following parameter had been used:

Input Voltage	: 10V
Output Voltage	: 5V – 20V
Inductor	: 2mH
Capacitor	: 10uF
Switching Frequency	: 50kHz

Simulation is mainly constructed to determine the parameter range and control system for the prototype development. The simulated design and output for the Buck Boost Converter is shown in Figure 2.

In this simulation the MOSFET is been used as a switch to control the circuit. The PI controller is used to control the Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) that are important in switching ON and OFF the MOSFET.

FIGURE 2: Simulated Circuit Diagram and the Output Waveform

The Buck Boost Converter is working based on the Duty Cycle that control the switch. When it is lower than 0.5 the circuit is in Buck Mode while when it is greater than 0.5 it is in Boost Mode

The simulated circuit proven both type of operating modes where it fall down to 5V in buck mode and rise up to 20V in boost mode. The PMW generated by comparing the output voltage and the step into PI controller that will set the duty cycle from a repeating sequence.

The simulated design is referred to develop a working prototype of the Buck Boost Converter

PROTOTYPE DEVELOPMENT

The development of prototype is important to show the ability of building a low cost Buck Boost Converter with stable control and in this process some decision of devices is done as following:

AVR Microcontroller	: ATTINY85
Operational Amplifier	: MCP602
Power MOSFET	: IRLZ44N
Schottky Diode	: 1N5819
Inductor	: 0.03mH
Capacitor	: 220uF
Voltage Regulator	: 7805

The use of AVR microcontroller helps to reduce the overall cost of the Buck Boost Converter where the microcontroller cost around RM4 per unit. The ability of it to generate PWM and built in ADC ease

the circuit control. FIGURE 3 will show the schematic of the developed Buck Boost Converter and on board prototype that been used for testing. The tested result is shown in FIGURE 4.

compared in order to generate the PWM signal to control the MOSFET switching.

FIGURE 3: Schematic of the developed prototype and circuit used for testing

FIGURE 4: Result for Duty Ratio and Output Voltage of the Buck Boost Converter

From FIGURE 4 the result show both reading for Duty Ratio and Output Voltage in Buck and Boost Mode. The reading show that for Duty Ratio of below 50% the converter is in Buck Mode. In this case with the duty ratio of 34% the reading of voltmeter is at 6.53V. The decline of Output Voltage from Input voltage show that the Buck mode works effectively. Meanwhile, when the reading of Duty Ratio exceed 50% the converter is in Boost Mode. In this case with the duty ratio of 80% the reading of voltmeter is at 54.13V. The incline of Output Voltage compared to Input Voltage shows the Boost mode work effectively.

The variation of Duty Ratio is important for controlling the Power MOSFET. The AVR Microcontroller had done this part effectively which can be seen in FIGURE 5. The Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) is generated directly from the microcontroller.

The AVR microcontroller is been programmed by an Arduino as In- System-Programmer. The clock of the microcontroller is set to generate a frequency of 32 kHz. The Analog Digital Converter(ADC) in the chip is programmed to read the value of feedback voltage and reference voltage. Both value then

FIGURE 5: Duty Ratio Variation

TESTING & ANALYSIS

The testing and analysis for the developed Buck Boost Converter is conducted before the fabrication process started. The load attached to the Output is being tested for several type of load for a verification. During this process, some modification from earlier circuit model is made and give out the current circuit model of Buck Boost Converter.

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CONCLUSION

This paper represent the study for development of a Buck Boost Converter with AVR microcontroller. The usage of MATLAB Simulink for simulation helps in making the process of prototype development easier. From the result obtain it can be concluded that:

- A controller in a system play an important part of the functionality of the system
- Output Voltage of a Buck Boost Converter can be smaller or bigger than input voltage according to the Duty Ratio that control the switching
- The Duty Ratio need to be lower than 50% to be in Buck mode and greater than 50% to be in Boost mode.
- AVR microcontroller ATtiny85 is a best microcontroller to be used in a Buck Boost Converter as it is very cheap and does not require complex DSP to control the circuit.
- The Duty Ratio for Boost need to be control to avoid the Output voltage become infinity

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